

The Last Line of Defense: Cyber Continuity Engineering

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Abstract— What will happen after a disastrous software failure or destructive cyberattack to your systems? Will service be restored quickly; can damage to stakeholders and customers be limited; will your organisation learn from the experience? We make a case for software professionals to engineer for ‘cyber continuity’ in addition to cybersecurity and reliability: identifying functionality and process improvements that, for appropriately low upfront cost, will limit the damage in the event of a disaster. We explore relevant literature and analyze how existing EU legislation is starting to require this of professionals. Using short case study examples, we propose four principles for software designers as first elements in a framework for cyber continuity engineering.

INTRODUCTION A recent study explored the 15-year future of cybersecurity for the UK’s critical national infrastructure [1]. From a Delphi study involving 22 experts, the results identified the most pressing challenges to be around the *response* to cyberattacks and other software disasters. It is indeed a huge issue: with the increasing dependence on software and large interconnected systems, the damage caused by a widespread software failure can be vast. Effective or ineffective responses to such a failure can affect its impact enormously.

It is of course vital that software professionals both adopt appropriate cybersecurity practices, and design and test systems around potential failure modes. However, it is now widely accepted that total security and total reliability are each virtually impossible—certainly at any practical cost. Accordingly, in this paper we explore what software engineers and systems technical teams can do to support an effective *response* to software disasters—

where all the hospital computers have failed, for example; where all the control systems for a country’s electricity supply are disabled; or where a major leak of sensitive data has already happened. What prior design or operational changes might reduce the disaster’s impact or support those responding to the disaster?

In starting to explore the topic in the cybersecurity community we encountered surprising tacit hostility to the concept. Engineers we spoke to confined their ideas and analysis to ways to *prevent* incidents; a reviewer of the Delphi study paper repeatedly demanded changes to its methodology to come up with a different conclusion; the cybersecurity industry has even tacitly redefined ‘resilience’ to mean only ‘disaster prevention’ without the ‘disaster survival and recovery’ elements it includes in other contexts [2].

The reason is not difficult to find. We software and cybersecurity professionals devote our life and work

to *preventing* cyber disaster. To even think about the implications *after* cyber disaster is anathema. Moreover, as technical experts, we have a strong, almost overriding, preference for technical, software only, solutions. Yet the response to a cyber disaster is certain to be human led, where professionals and others are dealing with an unexpected situation subject to huge stress. Planning for it takes us far from our comfort zone.

Yet, the continually increasing list of cyber disasters means that this mental toolkit is failing us. Increasingly, legislation is starting to require organizations to plan for disaster, especially in ‘critical infrastructure’ where an outage or data loss will have major consequences. The message is “Your software system or cybersecurity may fail. Plan for it.”

So, how are we as software professionals to ‘think the unthinkable’ and plan for disaster? How might we design a software system for a situation where it has failed, or design for a major loss of sensitive data? How best can a system empower the human experts who will have to deal with the disaster? In short, how can software engineering incorporate best practices in designing for disaster?

The remaining sections of this paper explore these questions: ‘Existing Research’ explores what we can learn from other domains and prior work; ‘Legislation’ motivates action by exploring European legislation around the subject; ‘Addressing the Problem’ offers a set of case studies and extracts cyber continuity techniques from them; and ‘Conclusion’ provides a summary and suggests future research.

Existing Research

This section explores work related to designing software and business systems to support the human response to disasters.

Surprisingly—or perhaps not, given the tacit opposition to the concept—we found very little in the cybersecurity literature. The NIST Cybersecurity framework, for example, offers promising functions as shown in Figure 1 but the scope of ‘Respond’ and ‘Recover’ are limited to stakeholder communication and getting systems running again:

Incident Recovery Plan Execution: Restoration activities are performed to ensure operational

Figure 1: NIST CSF Functions

availability of systems and services affected by cybersecurity incidents [3].

While these functions are vital, they nevertheless neglect the human aspects and any consideration of reducing the disaster’s impact. Indeed, the definition of resilience to mean purely and exclusively disaster prevention is reflected throughout the cyber resilience literature [4].

Among recent definitions of resilience most include the ability to continue to deliver, but no cyber resilience frameworks address the continuance of service or system recovery in any depth [4]. In practice, though, some organizations have started to plan for it, especially in the Transportation, Power Systems, Health Care and Finance domains [5].

Yet even to consider the problem at all seems relatively rare; a 2020 survey in Italy found only two out of six companies interviewed had a disaster recovery plan [6].

None of the frameworks or existing cyber-related literature consider changes to existing systems to help humans reduce the impact of a disaster [4]. It appears we need to look further afield for wider aspects of cyber disaster survival and recovery.

In doing so, we found relevant work in two areas: ‘Resilience Engineering’ as developed by the safety community; and ‘Business Continuity Planning’ research from management science. The following sections explore the implications for software design found in each.

Resilience Engineering Applied to Cyber

Resilience Engineering emerged in the 2000s as a new way of thinking in the safety domain. In contrast to a previous focus on removing dangers, Resilience

Figure 2: Cyber Resilience

Engineering focuses on enabling organizations and systems to carry on no matter what happens:

“Resilience is an expression of how people, alone or together, cope with everyday situations – large and small – by adjusting their performance to the conditions. An organization’s performance is resilient if it can function as required under expected and unexpected conditions alike” [7].

Resilience Engineering thus covers not just preventing damage, but surviving, recovering from, and learning from incidents. It includes preparing for, and mitigating, the external impacts of systems failure. It is dependent on organizational culture as well as technology.

Resilience engineering addresses the organization’s abilities, as shown in Figure 2:

- to respond to what happens,
- to monitor critical developments,
- to anticipate future threats and opportunities, and
- to learn from experience: successes as well as failures.

These are an impressive cornerstone to effective handling of software disasters. However, practitioners focus on the human aspects: changes to human organizations and processes are in scope; supporting changes to software systems appear to be ‘beneath the radar’ [7].

Business Continuity Applied to Cyber

The business continuity world has more to say on the subject.

Naturally, practical support for IT business continuity has been available in the literature for some time. The focus of such support is risk assessment, business impact analysis, and particularly backup and restore strategies [8]. Recently, though, a group of software and

management experts associated with the British Computer Society have been drawing attention to the strategic lack of planning and data gathering around large-scale IT failures. They have called for better data gathering and provide guidelines for companies to reduce the impact of such failures. In particular, they recommend the identification of critical business services, and workshops involving stakeholders [9].

Academic research on Business Continuity has been extensive, especially around the creation of a business continuity plan, but there has been little research around the human-centered aspects of surviving a cyber disaster [10].

This paper explores that research gap and the missing engineering discipline around it. In line with the literature above, we shall use the term ‘Cyber Continuity Engineering’ to mean the application of resilience engineering and business continuity methods to the design of software systems for effective human-centered disaster handling.

Legislation

This section motivates Cyber Continuity Engineering with reference to existing EU legislation. While the Cyber Security Act 2018 aimed purely to prevent successful cyberattacks, more recent legislation, specifically the NIS 2 directive, DORA, the Cyber Resilience Act, and the CER Directive have a wider remit, as follows.

The NIS 2 Directive

The NIS 2 directive [11], now in force, deals with network and information security in critical industries within the EU. It aims for *a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union*. The Directive follows the GDPR model in imposing large fines for non-compliance.

The Directive advocates that relevant organizations should adopt *appropriate and proportional technical, operational and organizational measures* that are *appropriate to the risks posed*. The list of desired measures includes *business continuity, such as backup management and disaster recovery, and crisis management*, though no advice is given on how these measures should be undertaken.

The Directive also recommends that member states should adopt policies *strengthening the cyber*

resilience and the cyber hygiene baseline of small and medium-sized enterprises, in particular those excluded from the scope of this Directive, by providing easily accessible guidance and assistance for their specific needs. We believe that the steps advocated in this work will be of particular use to such out-of-scope, under-resourced enterprises. Many probably cannot afford to implement the types of strategies recommended in NIS 2. However, their recovery prospects in emergency situations will be considerably enhanced if they consider the simple precautions suggested in this paper.

Digital Operational Resilience Act

The Digital Operational Resilience Act (DORA) for the Financial Sector [12] issues directions for the cybersecurity of the critically important financial industry. Risk management, the management, classification and reporting of adverse incidents, digital operation resilience testing, information sharing, assessing and managing third party service providers, and harmonizing the EU institutions created by this regulation and others, are all featured.

This legislation has specific provisions for cyber continuity. Individual businesses are instructed to put in place *ICT business continuity plans*, to regularly assess their ability to deal with unexpected and severe adverse events. There are some practical nuggets; financial entities are advised to *design the network connection infrastructure in a way that allows it to be instantaneously severed or segmented in order to minimize and prevent contagion*, for example, and to *have in place mechanisms to promptly detect anomalous activities...including automatic alert mechanisms for relevant staff in charge of ICT-related incident response*. Financial entities should be able to switch over to redundant systems. They should have backup and restoration capabilities which are tested “periodically”. There is mention of training. There is extensive discussion of Threat Led Penetration Testing (TLTP); where it applies, what it applies to, what bodies should undertake it, what bodies the results should be sent to, and what bodies should oversee the financial industry to make sure it is done. Some institutions must have redundant, fully provisioned secondary sites at a geographical distance from their primary site. There are numerous provisions for overseeing third-party service

providers, particularly those used by multiple institutions across multiple jurisdictions, and those based in third countries.

Overall, the Act reflects the complex concerns entailed in coordinating and shepherding cybersecurity regulation in over twenty separate jurisdictions for a huge and varied industry with critical importance for societal wellbeing. Most of the instructions, advice, and penalty recommendations are at this macro level.

There are excellent recommendations on incorporating into continuity plans any lessons learned or faults discovered during testing, during actual adverse events, or while following the current continuity plans. Response and recovery are mentioned frequently, and remediation plans are mandated. Mentions of the human side include the need to train staff on cybersecurity awareness and recovery, and to keep them informed during adverse events.

However, the practical implications of designing systems to support this response and remediation for human actors are not discussed, leaving a gap which we attempt to address in this paper.

The EU Cyber Resilience Act

The European Cyber Resilience Act [13] will apply from the end of 2027. Its aim is to make software in the EU, including within IoT devices, more secure during its useful lifetime. The legislation mandates an ability to update software for five years or the lifetime of the product, whichever is shorter. This can be used to act against newly discovered cyber threats or software defects. There are also development process disclosure and vulnerability reporting obligations. The Act states that *products with digital elements shall [...] protect the availability of essential and basic functions, also after an incident, including through resilience*.

There is no human-centered guidance here, such as tools or planning for the emergency responders; and a focus on the technical side of harm-reduction is evident throughout the Act. For example, products with digital elements should *“be designed, developed and produced to reduce the impact of an incident using appropriate exploitation mitigation mechanisms and techniques”*.

We suggest that to do this effectively requires analysis how such systems are used and will behave during an incident, bringing us into the realm of Cyber Continuity Engineering.

Resilience of Critical Entities Directive

The CER Directive [14] considers the resilience of critical entities within the EU in the context of disasters, including natural disasters but also including successful cyberattack. Resilience is defined as *ability to prevent, protect against, respond to, resist, mitigate, absorb, accommodate and recover from an incident*. EU critical entities are required to have resilience strategies such as a *resilience plan or equivalent* in place.

References to personnel are made mostly in the context of conducting security checks on them, though there is mention of assisting personnel to prepare for disaster via “training courses, information materials and exercises”.

The legislation, though, implies a need to build software in such a way as to facilitate effective human action during disaster situations.

Legislation Summary

Overall, in current EU legislation there is an implied or explicit duty for software creators and suppliers to facilitate business continuity; the legislation has some discussion of what this entails.

The importance of facilitating the human aspects of providing a restricted service and restoring a system’s functionality is implied by all the legislation explored here, and explored in detail in the DORA act. There is, therefore, a need to look in detail at the techniques and software aspects that allow human stakeholders to do this—in short, for Cyber Continuity Engineering.

Addressing the Problem

Whether an organization continues to deliver a service when their systems are compromised or destroyed will primarily depend on how staff and their stakeholders can work together to address the problems. Some of that work will be restoring the computer systems, but much will be delivering a ‘degraded’ service to those who depend on it. In every case, this involves humans responding constructively

to unexpected situations, which requires human decisions and human activity. So, Cyber Continuity Engineering is primarily human centered.

Specifically, Cyber Continuity Engineering is designing software systems and the human processes used around them to reduce the impact of disastrous failures.

To start to explore the discipline of Cyber Continuity Engineering, we can start from grounded practical examples. In the following sections, we sketch out some case studies of software disasters and distill possible principles from each. In each case, so far as we are aware, those responding to the crises acted competently and to the best of their professional ability. Since these are only sketched examples it is likely there were also good reasons for the decisions that led to each situation; rather than condemn past decisions, our suggested alternatives illustrate principles to help teams in future.

Canary Releases

CrowdStrike’s Falcon system provides weekly software security updates to a vast number of Microsoft Windows-based computers in companies worldwide [15]. On 19 July 2024, an erroneous update ‘bricked’ every machine it reached.

The authors have heard many cyber experts speaking on the subject, pointing to failures in testing, in the release control and in corporate governance. That is the ‘cyber defense’ approach to the problem. The Cyber Continuity Engineering approach to the same problem might be to point to the widespread Information Systems practice of updating a small subset of machines first before rolling out a full deployment. If CrowdStrike had incorporated such ‘canary releases’ into their process, the error would have been damaging but not remotely as catastrophic as what happened; CrowdStrike’s human operators would have seen to that.

Of course, there are practical and commercial implications to canary releases—how to select the subset in a way that is fair to customers, changes in the contractual terms, etc.—but the benefits we now know would have been huge.

Other examples of this way of thinking include:

- In load-balanced cluster systems, updating one server and waiting before updating the rest.

- Keeping different segments of networks segregated and updating software in one segment before others.

The Cyber Continuity Engineering principle is to identify places where software changes must happen in multiple systems, and to find ways to stagger those changes.

Honeytraps

In November 2013, hackers infiltrated Target's systems via a third-party heating contractor and installed malware on Target's point-of-sale terminals. They extracted payment card details for about 40 million customers during the Christmas shopping season. It was not until mid-December that U.S. Law Enforcement detected a problem, and Target announced the loss [16]. That meant there were several weeks during which criminals could use the card details undetected, causing major losses to customers.

A straightforward technique that could have detected the problem is a 'honeytrap': a fake software system or data item to draw attackers to reveal themselves, enabling the human owners of the systems to take appropriate action. In this case the implementation might be 'honey tokens': plausible but fake sets of card details, whose use alerts the payment card company. We found this software professional's description:

"I personally implemented [honey tokens] in a Bank, 20 years ago, generating some fake credit cards number (and other information) and having them being monitored [...]. We actually were able to catch internal people selling data and we could understand some ways data used to flow and work pretty tight with the Police to intercept and bust criminal groups" [17].

There are many other kinds of honey tokens, with different mechanisms to trigger an alert, for example:

- Fake accounts, omitted in normal marketing mailings, use of whose email address generates an alert;
- Fake documents, with embedded tracking pixels or similar, in a corporate document archive; and
- 'Trapdoor' files, with interesting names, generating an operating system alert if anyone reads them.

The Cyber Continuity Engineering principle we can generalize as identifying datasets of value if stolen and finding a way to 'honeytrap' them to generate an alert to the organisation in case of illicit use.

Exercising Backup Recovery

The British Library is the United Kingdom's main central library, retaining a copy of every book published in the UK and much else. Its computer systems were destroyed by a targeted ransomware attack in October 2023.

Despite an effective crisis management plan and intact offline backups, two years later many of its external-facing services were still unavailable. The library's outdated legacy systems could not be reinstated as before, and the backups proved incompatible with new, more secure, systems. The library's management concluded the following:

"Given that no security is perfect, the ability to quickly recover is essential when (not if) an attack is successful. Investment in security needs to be balanced against investment in back-up and recovery capabilities" [18].

There are various ways for operators to exercise backup recovery systems [19]:

- Trial restores, in which a separate system is restored from backup to an isolated recovery environment.
- Trials of 'warm standby' systems where the backup is available on a running machine and can be taken live.
- Including database restores into both the software developers' automated testing and the Quality Assurance team's validation of the software.

We deduce a Cyber Continuity Engineering principle to not only keep backups, but to exercise and test regular restores.

Paper Trail

When the shipping giant Maersk was hit by the NotPetya ransomware virus in 2017, almost all their software systems including those on-board ships were destroyed. But in accordance with normal procedures, most ships in transit had printed out hard copy documents of the customs and harbor documentation they needed for their next port. So, those ships could

continue their current voyages until they were safely docked in port. Other shipping continued with manually prepared paperwork taped to containers [20].

Of course, paper is not the only way to keep a local copy of the information required to keep providing a service. A suitably encrypted copy of the data on a disconnected device, in an widely supported format such as PDF, editable document or spreadsheet, would suffice for many contingencies. Examples might be:

- Patient operation lists for hospital surgical departments;
- Staff details for payroll; and even
- Taxpayer details for council tax demands.

Each of these, given some ingenuity and hard work on the part of the human professionals involved, could be enough for the most important organisation activities to continue. Though such preparations carry their own security concerns, the service continuity benefits are potentially huge.

We deduce a Cyber Continuity Engineering principle to explore situations where a secure local copy of operational data in easily readable form, whether paper or a well-supported digital format, might permit staff to continue providing a service through a system disaster.

Further Possibilities

We can identify other possibilities, including:

- For recovery, ensuring a system allows operators to enter ‘back dated’ transactions after a period of manual operation.
- Ensuring there are means for human override where this could make sense in an emergency.
- A ‘kill switch’, for administrators to turn off an infiltrated system to limit the potential damage.
- Finding ways to enable staff to run key sub-systems independently of the full interconnected system.

By discussing further past incidents with the experts involved, we expect to find many other learning points for Cyber Continuity Engineering.

Conclusion

Both legislation and business concerns increasingly require us to plan for the aftermath of cyber disasters: system failures and major data loss. Such planning can use both Business Continuity and Resilience Engineering frameworks and practices.

Exploring a range of past disaster scenarios, this paper identified four initial such Cyber Continuity Engineering techniques for system designers:

- **Canary Releases:** identifying places where software changes must happen in multiple systems and finding ways to stagger those changes.
- **Honey Traps:** identifying datasets of value if stolen and finding a way to incorporate ‘honey tokens’ to generate an alert to the organisation in case of illicit use.
- **Exercising Backups:** Exercising regular restores of backups and verifying the results.
- **Paper Trail:** finding situations where a secure local copy of operational data in easily readable form can permit staff to continue providing a service through a system disaster.

These techniques are relatively inexpensive, and plausible as activities to add to ‘business as usual’ work. Many more techniques are possible and can be identified through similar case study analysis and through leveraging expert knowledge.

We suggest a strong need for research to identify and taxonomize such techniques. Given those, we shall need research into ways to support software development teams, cybersecurity experts, and higher management to move their thinking from cyber defense alone to Cyber Continuity Engineering.

We look forward to this becoming a reality.

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